

Probabilistic Management of Uncertainty in Innovative Construction Projects

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Abstract

Deterministic planning in construction, based on methods such as deterministic CPM, does not incorporate the inherent uncertainty of projects, a limitation that is exacerbated in innovative scenarios such as 3D printing. This study compared a rural house built using conventional methods with one built using 3D printing, employing CPM scheduling and Monte Carlo simulations. The results demonstrate that probabilistic planning better represents schedule variability, whereas innovative methods, despite reducing average durations, exhibit greater dispersion. It was concluded that integrating probabilistic approaches strengthens project management and reliability.

Keywords: Project planning, Critical Path Method (CPM), Monte Carlo simulation, 3D printing.

Introduction

Traditionally, construction planning has been based on deterministic methods, such as CPM, which rely on prior experience, historical data, and general assumptions. Although useful, they present significant limitations; they do not systematically incorporate uncertainty and assume stable conditions throughout execution [1]. In practice, each project is unique and faces constant changes, causing initial schedules to often become obsolete, forcing rescheduling that increases costs, extends timeframes, and reduces productivity [2,3]. This problem is intensified in innovative projects, such as construction using 3D printing, where the absence of historical data and high technical variability amplify the uncertainty. In this context, those responsible for planning and risk management require more robust tools to

anticipate impacts and mitigate deviations in time and cost [4]. Probabilistic planning, supported by risk assessment methodologies, has emerged as a viable alternative to address this challenge [5].

Methodology

The study was conducted in three phases (Figure 1) to compare deterministic and probabilistic planning across two scenarios: a rural house built using conventional methods and the same house constructed using 3D printing. In the first phase, a deterministic schedule was developed using the CPM method; in the second, a probabilistic model was formulated based on the same network; and in the third, Monte Carlo simulations were applied to analyze the propagation of uncertainty. The evaluated construction prototypes are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Methodological workflow for schedule risk analysis.
Source: Created by the author

Figure 2. Rural Housing Prototypes: Conventional vs 3D Printing
Source: Created by the author

Results

In the conventional scenario, deterministic scheduling using CPM estimated a project duration of 57 days, whereas the probabilistic model showed that, with 90% confidence, construction could be extended between 55 and 63 days, with a maximum of 67 days. This indicates that probabilistic analysis allows the anticipation of deviations that are not captured by deterministic scheduling.

In the 3D printing scenario, CPM scheduling yielded 53 days; however, the probabilistic model indicated a range of 52–61 days and a maximum duration of 65 days (Figure 3). Although the central estimated time is shorter than that of the conventional method, the dispersion is greater, reflecting the uncertainty inherent in emerging technologies.

Figure 3. Probability distributions of construction durations for conventional and 3D printing scenarios.

Conclusions

The study demonstrated that deterministic planning provides fixed estimates that fail to capture real variability, whereas probabilistic models reflect wider ranges, particularly for emerging technologies such as 3D printing, where uncertainty is higher owing to their novel and evolving nature. Monte Carlo simulation proved to be an effective tool for anticipating risks and assessing schedule compliance probabilities.

For project managers and planners, the proposed framework provides a structured methodology for quantifying schedule risk beyond traditional CPM-based planning. By incorporating probabilistic modeling and Monte Carlo simulations, practitioners can better anticipate potential delays, allocate contingency buffers more effectively, and assess the

reliability of alternative construction technologies. This is particularly relevant for additive manufacturing applications, where uncertainties remain substantial.

This study is limited to a single housing prototype and relies on assumed probability distributions owing to the scarcity of empirical data on 3D printing construction processes. Future research should incorporate larger datasets from real projects, extend the framework to include cost and resource uncertainty, and investigate correlations among activities. Additionally, the integration of real-time data acquisition and digital twins could further enhance predictive accuracy.

This research contributes a hybrid deterministic–probabilistic scheduling framework that combines the CPM with Monte Carlo simulation to explicitly quantify construction duration uncertainty. This study provides comparative insights between conventional and 3D-printed housing scenarios, offering empirical evidence of increased variability in emerging construction technologies and demonstrating the value of stochastic methods for advanced construction planning.

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